

Assessment of Maternal Health Literacy of Women Attending Antenatal Healthcare in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

There is need to understand maternal health literacy (MHL) among pregnant women, as adequate literacy is crucial for positive pregnancy outcomes. This study assessed the maternal health literacy of women attending antenatal healthcare services in Ekiti State. A cross-sectional design was used to sample 239 pregnant women aged 15–49 years from primary healthcare centres across Ekiti Central Senatorial District. A multistage sampling procedure selected the district, local government areas, healthcare facilities, and Participants, ensuring proportional representation. Data were collected using a structured and validated questionnaire adapted from NNDHS (2018) and WHO (2016), translated into Yoruba for ease of comprehension. The tool assessed socio-demographic characteristics and various dimensions of MHL, including the ability to locate, understand, and use health information. Reliability testing produced a Cronbach's alpha of 0.783. Data were analysed using SPSS version 25, employing descriptive statistics. Ethical approval was obtained from relevant institutional committees, and informed consent was secured from all Participants. The findings showed that the mean age of Participants was 29.32 ± 6.18 years, with the majority possessing at least secondary education. Overall, 56.5% demonstrated moderate maternal health literacy, 40.2% had high literacy, and 3.3% showed low literacy. Strengths were observed in basic literacy, maternal care knowledge, and nutrition awareness, whereas challenges emerged in interpreting prescriptions, searching for health information, understanding appointment dates, and identifying danger signs in pregnancy. The study concluded that most women possessed moderate MHL related to pregnancy nutrition, with a small proportion demonstrating high literacy.

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Introduction

Maternal Health Literacy (MHL), an important predictor of maternal and neonatal health, is the specific set of knowledge and social skills that enables individuals to know the symptoms of risk to pregnancy, adopt health practices, and make decisions to increase access to quality prenatal care (Andong et al., 2023). In the context of antenatal healthcare, this construct is of particular significance as women's agency in navigating the health system, interpreting medical advice, and translating relevant health information has a direct impact on pregnancy outcomes. Research is also consistent in demonstrating that higher levels of maternal health literacy is associated with lower levels of negative birth outcomes for women, such as premature birth, low birth weight and neonatal mortality (Jarvie et al., 2025). Pregnancy is a physiologically sensitive period that is associated with changes in biochemical and anatomical processes, which can put the woman and the unborn child at a high risk. These physiological changes can have profound implications for the woman's quality of life (QoL), physical functioning, ability to cope with stress and overall pregnancy experience (Alamirew et al., 2024). Access to reliable, full, and timely health information, therefore, is key to ensuring healthy pregnancy outcomes.

Pregnant women in Ekiti State as well as most anywhere in Nigeria, where traditional support systems are becoming increasingly unreliable, are increasingly tasked with the responsibility of finding out on their own information pertaining to achieving safe motherhood. Olatunde and Arogundade (2024) noted that lack of maternal knowledge in most developing regions still has an impact on maternal QoL and child wellbeing. However, access to quality health information has been proven to be a major contributor to improved maternal outcomes. Antenatal clinic (ANC) is the main formal platform for dissemination of such information, but research suggests that information needs of pregnant women are not met during routine ANC visits. Studies have reported trends of poor communication between pregnant women and healthcare providers during antenatal consultations (Kraemer et al., 2023), leading to a partial or complete lack of delivery of important health messages. Many women go to ANC anticipating extensive information on drugs, nutrition, danger signs and life-style. Instead, they are provided with short instructions due to time limitations, high patient load or lack of patient-centred communication practices.

This lack of communication forces many pregnant women to go outside of their healthcare professional to get their own information, especially the internet. Recent studies in Nigeria have revealed that women commonly use online resources to ease pregnancy-related issues, understand drug administration and receive instructions on postnatal issues (Adeoye & Okekunle, 2022; Bello et al., 2022). Whilst digital information-seeking behaviour might empower some women, it also creates risks of misinformation, misinterpretation or reliance on non-evidence-based content. Pregnant women need to be provided with evidence-based information to enable them to make informed decisions about diet, lifestyle, medication safety, and the identification of danger signs (Adewuyi et al., 2024). However, many have indicated the need for more detailed explanations than are typically provided in a clinical setting (Akinrinmade et al., 2024). To make matters worse, it has been noted that some healthcare providers do not sufficiently discuss or respond to patients' queries, further hindering communication and discouraging them from asking more questions. This lack of communication does not allow women to be adequately involved in decisions regarding their pregnancy care.

In Nigeria, poor maternal health literacy is still a major problem. There is a constant shortage of health information needed during antenatal care, which has been found to contribute to low uptake of the available health services and impedes the empowerment of pregnant women. The provision of accurate, relevant and understandable health information to pregnant women in Ekiti State is a necessary step for strengthening a healthy human capital and reducing avoidable maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality. High maternal health literacy facilitates early registration for ANC, compliance with medical instructions, appropriate dietary practices, safe use of medications and danger signs recognition-all of which enable reduction in morbidity and mortality.

Maternal health literacy also supports the acquisition of knowledge on the ANC components. Several Nigerian studies have shown marked variation in the level of knowledge in different regions. For instance, Bello et al. (2022) reported that 41.6% of new mothers in Ekiti State had low level of maternal health literacy which was linked to delay in care as only 55.7% registered for antenatal clinic (ANC) during the first 14 weeks of gestation. Conversely, it was found markedly higher general awareness in Ido-Ekiti, with 95.6% of women being aware of ANC services, with over 97% being able to point out ANC basic components like regular blood tests, physical examination and micronutrient supplementation. These conflicting results within the same geographical state emphasize the need for a specific evaluation of maternal health literacy for antenatal attendees in Ekiti.

While it was documented that ANC awareness was lower for most of the population, trends are similar in the international literature where general awareness of the ANC tends to be higher in settings with better access to education. For instance, an Eritrean study found that 84% of mothers had good ANC knowledge (Gebremariam et al. 2023), and Bashir et al (2023) reported that 96% of pregnant women in the South Asian region had a minimum average knowledge of ANC services. However, upon more in-depth analysis, it is still found that there are continuing gaps in specific areas of maternal health literacy. In Nigeria, for example, only 35.5% of women had been found to have good knowledge of safe use of drugs during pregnancy (Obi & Anosike, 2023) a statistic that is a cause of alarm because of the implications of inappropriate drug use. Besides, in Ethiopia, Gebremichael and Belachew Lema (2023) have shown that the odds of having good dietary diversity were significantly higher among women with good nutritional knowledge (AOR ~ 3.3), thus directly linking maternal health literacy with behavioural outcomes.

These results as a whole point to the conclusion that although basic ANC knowledge is widespread in some communities (Jesuyajolu et al., 2022 and Bashir et al., 2023), knowledge about specific details (nutritional knowledge, supplement use, warning signs, and medication safety) is both inconsistent and lacking. The available evidence in Ekiti State suggests that low levels of maternal literacy could directly lead to the delay in seeking care and negative health outcomes for mother and child (Bello et al., 2022). These gaps underline the importance of conducting a comprehensive analysis of maternal health literacy among women attending antenatal clinics in the state. Such evaluation is not only important for identifying patterns of knowledge gaps, but also for driving target interventions for reinforcing communication interventions, enhancing provider-patient interactions, and improving the overall quality of antenatal health services delivery.

In view of the importance of maternal health literacy in determining the outcome of pregnancy, this study aims to give a thorough assessment of pregnancy-related health literacy of women who are attending antenatal healthcare in Ekiti State.

The aim of this study is to assess maternal health literacy of women attending antenatal healthcare in Ekiti state.

Research Methods

The study employed a cross-sectional research design to assess maternal health literacy among pregnant women attending antenatal healthcare services in Ekiti State. The target population comprised women receiving antenatal care at primary healthcare centres located across rural and urban areas of the state. Given that over 10,000 pregnant women were registered in these centres and the population variance was unknown, Ekiti Central Senatorial District was purposefully selected, consisting of five local government areas: Ado, Irepodun/Ifelodun, Ekiti West, Efon, and Ijero. Only pregnant women aged 15–49 years, willing to participate, and currently receiving antenatal care were included, whereas women unwilling to participate or too agitated were excluded. To determine the sample size, the Taro Yamane formula was applied using a 5% margin of error, and the result was adjusted for 10% non-response, producing a final sample size of 239 participants.

Sampling followed a multistage procedure. First, simple random sampling selected Ekiti Central from the three senatorial districts in the state. All five local governments in the district were then selected using the same method. In the third stage, fifteen primary healthcare centres offering antenatal services were chosen, three from each local government area. Finally, systematic random sampling was applied in each facility, where every third pregnant woman attending antenatal care was selected until the allocated sample size per facility was reached. The distribution of participants across centres was proportional to the volume of pregnant women attending each facility monthly, ensuring appropriate representation. This approach enabled the study to capture a diverse group of women from different service points within the selected district.

The research instrument consisted of a structured questionnaire adapted from validated tools, including NNDHS (2018) and WHO (2016), and modified to suit the study objectives. The tool was translated into Yoruba to accommodate participants who could not read English. Section A captured socio-demographic characteristics through 12 items, such as age, marital status, education, occupation, household income, family size, and spouse's details. Section B focused on maternal health literacy and contained 14 items measured on a four-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Items assessed women's ability to locate, understand, and interpret health information, read prescriptions, and comprehend medical appointments. The questionnaire's face and content validity were established by experts in nursing and measurement, whose feedback guided clarity, relevance, and phrasing adjustments. Reliability testing through a pilot study conducted at Ilawe-Ekiti with 40 participants yielded a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.783, confirming strong internal consistency.

Data collection involved the direct administration of questionnaires by the researcher and two trained research assistants. Training was conducted one day before data collection to ensure a clear understanding of the study objectives, recruitment procedures, and administration of the instrument. Questionnaires were distributed only after obtaining voluntary informed consent from participants. Completed questionnaires were checked for

completeness, cleaned, and coded before being entered into Microsoft Excel. The processed data was exported to SPSS version 25 for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and percentages, were employed to address the study objectives, and the results were presented in tables for clarity.

Ethical considerations were addressed in accordance with institutional and state regulations. The researcher obtained an introductory letter from the Faculty of Nursing, Afe Babalola University, and ethical approval from the Health Research and Ethical Review Committee of the College of Medicine and Health Sciences (ABUAD). This approval and the research proposal were submitted to the Ethics and Research Committee of the Ekiti State Primary Health Care Development Agency for further clearance. Participants were adequately informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and confidentiality measures. Both verbal and written consent were obtained before data collection. They were assured that participation was voluntary, anonymity was guaranteed, and they had the right to withdraw from the study at any point.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants and their spouses (N=239)

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age group (Mean \pm SD = 29.32 \pm 6.18)	< 20	8	3.3
	20-24	41	17.2
	25-29	88	36.8
	30-34	52	21.8
	35-39	29	12.1
	> 40	21	8.8
Marital status	Living with spouse	193	80.8
	Not living with spouse	46	19.2
Ethnicity	Igbo	40	16.7
	Yoruba	139	58.2
	Hausa	40	16.7
	Ebira	9	3.8
	Igede	11	4.6
	Religion	Christianity	194
Educational status	Islam	39	16.3
	Traditionalist	6	2.5
	No formal education	9	3.8
	Primary education	38	15.9
Occupation	Secondary education	103	43.1
	Tertiary education	89	37.2
	Unemployed	52	21.8
	Self-employed	101	42.3
	Civil servant	64	26.8
Household monthly income	Private sector employee	22	9.2
	< 70,000	119	49.8
	71,000-200,000	91	38.1
	> 201,000	29	12.1

Family size	1-3	175	73.2
	4 or more	64	26.8
Family type	Single parent	89	37.2
	Nuclear	147	61.5
	Extended	3	1.3
Spouse's educational level	No formal education	26	10.9
	Primary education	24	10.0
	Secondary education	91	38.1
	Tertiary education	98	41.0
Spouse's occupation	Unemployed	66	27.6
	Self-employed	103	43.1
	Civil servant	44	18.4
	Private sector employee	26	10.9
	Total	239	100.0
Estimated spouse's annual income	< 70,000	119	49.8
	71,000-200,000	91	38.1
	> 201,000	29	12.1
	Total	239	100.0

The participants had a mean age of 29.32 years, with most (36.8%) aged 25–29 years, and the majority (80.8%) living with their spouses. Yoruba women constituted the largest ethnic group (58.2%), while Christianity was the predominant religion (81.2%). Most participants had at least secondary education (43.1%), and 37.2% had tertiary education; their spouses also largely attained secondary (38.1%) or tertiary education (41.0%). The participants were mainly self-employed (42.3%), though 21.8% were unemployed. Nearly half of the households (49.8%) earned below ₦70,000 monthly, and most families (73.2%) had between one and three members, with nuclear families accounting for 61.5%. Spouses were predominantly self-employed (43.1%), and their income distribution mirrored that of the participants, with 49.8% earning below ₦70,000 annually.

Figure 1: Level of maternal literacy among pregnant women

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of maternal health literacy levels among pregnant women. A majority of the Participants, 56.5%, were categorised as having a medium level of health literacy, indicating a moderate ability to access, understand, and use health-related information. Additionally, 40.2% of the Participants demonstrated a high level of maternal health literacy, suggesting that they are well-equipped to make informed decisions regarding their health and that of their babies. Only 3.3% of the women were found to have low maternal health literacy, reflecting a limited capacity to comprehend and apply health information.

Table 2: Level of maternal health literacy among participants (N=239)

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean ± SD
I cannot look for health information in a library or on the Internet	78(32.6)	51(21.3)	82(34.3)	28(11.7)	2.75±1.04
I can understand and interpret basic health information	82(34.3)	121(50.6)	23(9.6)	13(5.4)	3.14±0.80
I cannot read, understand & interpret medical prescriptions or instructions accurately	37(15.5)	62(25.9)	108(45.2)	32(13.4)	2.44±0.91
I cannot read and understand dates of medical appointments (such as dates of antenatal, immunisation, screening, and physical examination)	53(22.2)	36(15.1)	98(41.0)	52(21.8)	2.38±1.06
I have a basic understanding of medical terms	73(30.5)	116(48.5)	33(13.8)	17(7.1)	3.03±0.86
I can read and understand health pamphlets correctly	86(36.0)	119(49.8)	24(10.0)	10(4.2)	3.18±0.77
I have adequate knowledge of diets to take during pregnancy and after delivery	90(37.7)	114(47.7)	25(10.5)	10(4.2)	3.19±0.79
I cannot read and understand danger signs in pregnancy (such as anaemia, pallor, raised BP, swelling, bleeding, early labour, etc.)	49(20.5)	49(20.5)	94(39.3)	47(19.7)	2.42±1.03
I can read, write and do basic numeric skills	101(42.3)	111(46.4)	20(8.4)	7(2.9)	3.28±0.74
I understand the difference in antenatal and delivery places with skilled and those without skilled birth attendants.	80(33.5)	116(48.5)	34(14.2)	9(3.8)	3.12±0.79
I have ability to read, understand and act on the health care information positively	84(35.1)	125(52.3)	20(8.4)	10(4.2)	3.18±0.76

I have adequate knowledge and skills on how to care for my baby after delivery (breastfeeding, bathing)	92(38.5)	119(49.8)	17(7.1)	11(4.6)	3.22±0.77
I can read health pamphlets and acquire information and skills to maintain personal and food hygiene during pregnancy and after delivery	87(36.4)	121(50.6)	20(8.4)	11(4.6)	3.19±0.77
I have adequate skills to prepare a balanced diet	89(37.2)	106(44.4)	33(13.8)	11(4.6)	3.14±0.82

* SA: Strongly agreed, A: Agreed, D: Disagreed, SD: Strongly disagreed, SD: Standard deviation

The findings from table 2 show the level of maternal health literacy among pregnant women. The majority reported confidence in basic literacy and numeracy skills, with 101 (42.3%) strongly agreeing and 111 (46.4%) agreeing that they could read, write, and perform basic numeric tasks (mean = 3.28 ± 0.74). Similarly, many Participants indicated that they possessed the ability to read, understand, and act positively on healthcare information, as shown by 84 (35.1%) who strongly agreed and 125 (52.3%) who agreed (mean = 3.18 ± 0.76). Most women also acknowledged having adequate knowledge and skills related to maternal and child care. For example, 92 (38.5%) strongly agreed and 119 (49.8%) agreed that they knew how to care for their babies after delivery, including practices such as breastfeeding and bathing (mean = 3.22 ± 0.77). Likewise, 90 (37.7%) strongly agreed and 114 (47.7%) agreed that they had good knowledge of appropriate diets during pregnancy and postpartum (mean = 3.19 ± 0.79). Additionally, 87 (36.4%) and 121 (50.6%) reported they could acquire relevant information from health pamphlets to maintain personal and food hygiene during and after pregnancy (mean = 3.19 ± 0.77).

Participants also showed substantial understanding of essential health concepts. For instance, 80 (33.5%) strongly agreed and 116 (48.5%) agreed that they understood the difference between skilled and unskilled birth attendants (mean = 3.12 ± 0.79), and 82 (34.3%) strongly agreed and 121 (50.6%) agreed that they could understand and interpret basic health information (mean = 3.14 ± 0.80). A notable number also expressed familiarity with medical terms, with 73 (30.5%) strongly agreeing and 116 (48.5%) agreeing (mean = 3.03 ± 0.86). On the contrary, some Participants expressed limitations in specific literacy areas. For instance, 78 (32.6%) strongly agreed and 51 (21.3%) agreed that they could not search for health information in a library or on the internet (mean = 2.75 ± 1.04). Similarly, 37 (15.5%) strongly agreed and 62 (25.9%) agreed that they could not accurately read and interpret medical prescriptions (mean = 2.44 ± 0.91), and 53 (22.2%) strongly agreed along with 36 (15.1%) agreeing that they could not understand dates for medical appointments such as antenatal visits or immunisations (mean = 2.38 ± 1.06). Another area of concern was the ability to identify danger signs in pregnancy, where 49 (20.5%) strongly agreed and another 49 (20.5%) agreed that they could not recognise these symptoms (mean = 2.42 ± 1.03).

Discussion of Findings

This study found that most participants were young, with an average age of 29 years, reflecting trends reported in Ibadan where most pregnant women were under 30 years (Adebayo et al., 2024). A majority lived with their spouses and were predominantly Yoruba, consistent with earlier findings in Southwestern Nigeria (Bello et al., 2022; Adeyemi et al.,

2023). Self-employment was common, aligning with patterns observed among women in urban and peri-urban settings (Afolabi et al., 2023). Nearly half of the participants earned below ₦70,000 monthly, indicating widespread economic challenges similar to national estimates (World Bank, 2024).

The study demonstrated generally positive maternal health literacy (MHL) levels among pregnant women, with over 88% reporting competence in basic reading, writing, and numeracy skills, which form the foundation for comprehending and utilising health information (Kaufman et al., 2021). Most Participants also showed strong understanding of maternal and child health issues, including breastfeeding, baby care, and nutrition during pregnancy and postpartum. More than 80% agreed or strongly agreed that they possessed the skills necessary for preparing balanced meals, caring for newborns, and interpreting basic health materials. These findings contrast with prior studies that identified widespread gaps in maternal knowledge, particularly in areas such as dietary planning and pamphlet interpretation (Bello et al., 2022). In this sample, maternal health knowledge appeared comparatively higher. However, despite these encouraging levels of functional knowledge, challenges persisted in advanced literacy domains. A notable proportion of women lacked confidence in navigating complex health information, demonstrating that high functional literacy did not always translate into critical or interactive literacy.

Substantial gaps were identified, particularly in accessing, interpreting, and applying more technical health information. Almost 54% of Participants reported an inability to search for health information in libraries or online, and over 40% struggled with interpreting medical prescriptions or understanding appointment dates. These findings reflect earlier research documenting limited MHL in areas such as interpreting health instructions, maintaining hygienic practices, and independently accessing health information (Nawabi et al., 2021; Bello et al., 2022). Additionally, 41% of Participants indicated that they could not identify danger signs in pregnancy, which is concerning given the potential consequences for maternal and neonatal outcomes. Inadequate MHL is recognised as a major contributor to delayed care-seeking and poor decision-making during antenatal and postnatal periods (Adepoju et al., 2020; Nawabi et al., 2021). In this study, 41.6% of women were classified as having inadequate MHL, consistent with estimates from multiple settings that report low or inadequate literacy among 30% to 80% of pregnant women (Ghanbari et al., 2020; Phommachanh et al., 2021). These gaps reinforce the need for improved MHL interventions to ensure equitable access to health information and empower women to make informed decisions critical to maternal and neonatal survival.

The findings showed that the majority of women possessed moderate to high levels of MHL, with 56.5% classified as medium and 40.2% as high, while only 3.3% exhibited low literacy levels. This distribution aligns with global estimates where 50–60% of pregnant women demonstrate adequate or high literacy (Phommachanh et al., 2021; Ghotbizadeh et al., 2022). The confidence in basic literacy and numeracy skills, reported by nearly 89% of Participants, surpassed figures observed in several low- and middle-income countries (Bello et al., 2022). Furthermore, 87.4% expressed the ability to understand and act on health information, mirroring results from Kenya and Ethiopia (Tesfaye et al., 2023). Knowledge of maternal and child health practices was also high, with close to 88% demonstrating adequate understanding, consistent with evidence from Ghana and Southeast Asia (Owusu & Mensah, 2023). Nevertheless, the persistent difficulties in searching for health information,

interpreting prescriptions, understanding appointments, and recognising pregnancy danger signs reveal critical weaknesses. Previous research in Tanzania and other low-resource settings similarly reported that 20–40% of women struggle with these tasks (Mollel et al., 2024). These findings highlight the need for targeted, context-specific interventions that strengthen advanced MHL skills to support safer pregnancy experiences and improved maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the majority of pregnant women possessed moderate maternal health literacy related to nutrition during pregnancy, with more than average demonstrating average knowledge levels and only a small proportion exhibiting high literacy.

Recommendations

1. The government should strengthen targeted nutrition education programmes within antenatal services to improve pregnant women’s understanding of dietary requirements and help those with average literacy attain higher competency.
2. Health facilities should integrate simplified and culturally appropriate nutrition materials such as visual guides, portion charts, and translated pamphlets into routine maternal care to enhance comprehension among women with moderate literacy levels.
3. Healthcare workers should receive continuous training to ensure they communicate nutrition information clearly, consistently, and in a user-friendly manner during antenatal visits.
4. Community health authorities and local NGOs should implement community-based outreach initiatives, including nutrition counselling and support groups, to reinforce key dietary messages and reach women with limited access to formal health education.

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